

Updating the line shape parameters for CO₂ broadened by air and CO₂

With an exception of 4300-7000 cm⁻¹ region the current air-broadening, temperature dependences of broadening and the air- shift coefficients of carbon dioxide in the HITRAN database [1] are based on the semi-empirical calculations by R. Gamache et al. [2] using Voigt profile. We collected the recent experimental results analyzed with the speed dependent Voigt profile. We used HAPI [3] to simulate the experimental spectra as well shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Simulation of experimental transmission of CO₂-air (measured by Keeyoon Sung) with HAPI using Voigt and speed dependent Voigt profiles. The bottom panels show the residuals for Voigt and speed dependent Voigt respectively.

As the plot shows simulation of spectra with SDV profile could not improve the residuals noticeably. It means that line mixing is needed to be taken into account for reducing the residuals. The Figure 2 presents that how considering SD and line mixing helps in improving the results.

Figure 2: Simulation of experimental transmission of CO₂-air (measured by Keeyoon Sung) with HAPI using speed dependent Voigt profile and speed dependent Voigt including line mixing parameter (the orange one).

Also, the current self and air-shift values in HITRAN2016 calculated based on the semi-empirical model by Gamache et al [2], do not present the asymmetric behavior in P and R branches. Therefore, we needed to substitute them with the experimental results wherever possible and make corrections to the semi-empirical model of Gamache et al.

Figure 3: Air-shift parameters for few bands of CO₂ in HITRAN 2016 compared to experimental measurements by Devi et al. [4, 5]

The details of the updated values for line shape parameters are described as follows:

- The **air- and self- broadening, their associated temperature dependence and air- and self-shift and their associated temperature dependence** parameters for **all the bands except 1.6micron region** updated using Ref. [4] ([GlobRef 1240]).
- The **air- and self- broadening, their associated temperature dependence and air- and self-shift and their associated temperature dependence** parameters for **30013-00001 (1.6 micron)** updated using Ref. [5] ([GlobRef 1241]).
- The **self- speed dependent parameters** for **all the bands and first order line mixing** parameter for **the 21102-00001 band** updated using Ref. [6] ([GlobRef 1242]).
- The **(N₂)- speed dependence** and the **temperature dependence of speed dependent** parameter for **all the bands** updated using Ref. [7] ([GlobRef 1243]).

Figure 4: The existing air-speed dependent parameters for few bands of CO₂ [4,5,7-9] respectively

In the above-mentioned papers only transitions with the even J'' values are reported (because most of the stronger lines belong to the bands with involve ground electronic state where due to nuclear spin statistics only even rotational levels are populated). In order to find the values of parameters for the transitions that involve the **odd J'' numbers**, we interpolated the experimental results reported for even J'' numbers and found the values for the odd ones. Below, sample fits are presented with the fitting equations:

Polynomial fit to the experimental values for air- broadening, temperature dependence of broadening and air- shift parameters obtained using qSDV profile [4, 5] ([GlobRef 1244: This reference])

- **2.06 μm region:**

$$\gamma_{\text{air}} = 0.09516 - 0.00192|m| + 5.351E-5|m|^2 - 6.921E-7|m|^3 + 3.161E-9|m|^4$$

$$\text{P branch: } \delta_{\text{air}} = -0.00241 + 3.1301E-4m + 1.1688E-5m^2 + 1.887E-7m^3 + 1.0861E-9m^4$$

$$\text{R branch: } \delta_{\text{air}} = -0.00293 - 9.375E-5m + 1.412E-6m^2 - 2.397E-8m^3 + 1.263E-10m^4$$

$$\text{P branch: } n_{\text{air}} = 0.736 + 0.0058m + 4.668E-4m^2 + 9.419E-6m^3 + 5.352E-8m^4$$

$$\text{R branch: } n_{\text{air}} = 0.7276 - 0.0056m + 4.457E-4m^2 - 8.6924E-6m^3 + 4.731E-8m^4$$

$$\text{P branch: } \delta_{\text{Pair}} = -1.59E-5 - 2.655E-6m - 1.437E-7m^2 - 3.0156E-9m^3 - 2.144E-11m^4$$

$$\text{R branch: } \delta_{\text{Pair}} = -3.805E-6 - 1.776E-6m + 1.424E-7m^2 - 3.599E-9m^3 + 3.055E-11m^4$$

- **1.6 μm region:**

$$\gamma_{\text{air}} = 0.09373 - 0.00171|m| + 3.963E-5|m|^2 - 3.716E-7|m|^3 + 8.919E-9|m|^4$$

$$\text{P branch: } \delta_{\text{air}} = -0.00253 + 3.487E-4m + 1.057E-5m^2 + 1.0337E-7m^3 - 2.848E-11m^4$$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{air}} = -0.00273 - 3.879E-4m + 2.376E-5m^2 - 6.167E-7m^3 + 5.016E-9m^4$

P branch: $n_{\text{air}} = 0.7231 + 0.00682m + 6.1179E-4m^2 + 1.329E-5m^3 + 8.264E-8m^4$

R branch: $n_{\text{air}} = 0.745 - 0.012m + 9.233E-4m^2 - 1.994E-5m^3 + 1.298E-7m^4$

P branch: $\delta_{\text{Pair}} = 9.246E-6 - 1.605E-6m + 4.30E-9m^2 + 2.82E-9m^3 + 4.617E-11m^4$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{Pair}} = 2.106E-5 - 2.269E-6m + 2.012E-7m^2 - 5.534E-9m^3 + 4.84E-11m^4$

The N₂- Speed dependent parameters and their temperature dependencies [7] ([GlobRef 1244: This reference]):

P branch: $SD_{\text{air}} = 0.07036 - 0.00262m - 1.524E-4m^2 - 2.845E-6m^3 - 1.704E-8m^4$

R branch: $SD_{\text{air}} = 0.07214 + 0.00205m - 9.834E-5m^2 + 1.0837E-6m^3 + 1.159E-8m^4$

P branch: $n_{SD_{\text{air}}} = 0.7563 + 0.00521m - 0.00149m^2 - 3.743E-5m^3$

R branch: $n_{SD_{\text{air}}} = 0.8192 - 0.0226m - 5.235E-4m^2 + 2.42E-5m^3$

The self- Speed dependence parameter [6] ([GlobRef 1244: This reference]):

P branch: $SD_{\text{self}} = 0.1103 + 0.0047m + 5.261E-4m^2 + 1.496E-5m^3 + 1.277E-7m^4$

R branch: $SD_{\text{self}} = 0.0691 + 0.0143m - 9.9592E-4m^2 + 2.99E-5m^3 - 4.258E-7m^4 + 2.325E-9m^5$

Q branch: $SD_{\text{self}} = 0.2838 - 0.0116m - 3.442E-4m^2 + 4.178E-5m^3 - 7.931E-7m^4$

The first order line mixing parameter [6] ([GlobRef 1244: This reference]):

P branch: $Y_{SDV_{\text{self}}} = -0.0162 + 0.00604m + 5.556E-4m^2 + 1.4865E-5m^3 + 1.268E-7m^4$

R branch: $Y_{SDV_{\text{self}}} = 0.0076 + 0.00198m - 1.721E-4m^2 + 3.965E-6m^3 - 2.757E-8m^4$

Q branch: $Y_{SDV_{\text{self}}} = 2.867 - 0.5688m + 0.03697m^2 - 9.865E-4m^3 + 9.253E-6m^4$

Polynomial fit to the experimental values for self- broadening, temperature dependence of broadening and air- shift parameters obtained using qSDV profile [4, 5] ([GlobRef 1244: This reference])

- **2.06 μm region:**

$\gamma_{\text{self}} = 0.1275 - 0.00189|m| + 2.858E-5|m|^2 - 2.849E-7|m|^3 + 1.162E-9|m|^4$

P branch: $\delta_{\text{self}} = -0.00631 - 3.726E-5m - 3.999E-6m^2 - 8.006E-8m^3 - 5.822E-10m^4$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{self}} = -0.00601 + 3.51E-5m - 5.256E-6m^2 + 9.698E-8m^3 - 5.799E-10m^4$

P branch: $n_{\text{self}} = 0.699 - 0.0104m - 0.0014m^2 - 4.34E-5m^3 - 5.305E-7m^4 - 2.205E-9m^5$

R branch: $n_{\text{self}} = 0.7293 + 0.00523m - 0.00102m^2 + 3.48E-5m^3 - 4.326E-7m^4 + 1.8E-9m^5$

P branch: $\delta_{P_{\text{self}}} = -3.07E-5 + 2.579E-6m + 2.688E-7m^2 + 5.937E-9m^3 + 3.738E-11m^4$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{Pself}}=-3.041\text{E-}5-1.676\text{E-}6m+1.48\text{E-}7m^2-1.77\text{E-}9m^3-4.27\text{E-}12m^4$

1.6 μm region:

$\gamma_{\text{self}}=0.1251-0.00169|m|+2.323\text{E-}5|m|^2-2.613\text{E-}7|m|^3+1.394\text{E-}9|m|^4$

P branch: $\delta_{\text{self}}=-0.0025+4.92\text{E-}4m+2.625\text{E-}5m^2+6.498\text{E-}7m^3+5.34\text{E-}9m^4$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{self}}=-0.00407-2.87\text{E-}4m+1.925\text{E-}5m^2-6.084\text{E-}7m^3+5.66\text{E-}9m^4$

P branch: $n_{\text{self}}=0.698-0.0242m-0.00238m^2-7.411\text{E-}5m^3-9.194-7m^4-3.931\text{E-}9m^5$

R branch: $n_{\text{self}}=0.749+0.00203m-1.727\text{E-}4m^2-1.0192\text{E-}5m^3+4.516\text{E-}7m^4-4.059\text{E-}9m^5$

P branch: $\delta_{\text{Pself}}=-1.33\text{E-}5+1.0309\text{E-}6m+3.89\text{E-}8m^2-8.571\text{E-}10m^3-1.87\text{E-}11m^4$

R branch: $\delta_{\text{Pself}}=-2.131\text{E-}5-2.141\text{E-}6m+1.96\text{E-}7m^2-4.016\text{E-}9m^3+2.513\text{E-}11m^4$

The tables are created in JSON file format to be updated in HITRAN.

References

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